

Appendix G: CO-OCCURRENCE ANALYSIS TABLES

Co-occurrence between Detect vs Identify

	Asset Management	Improvement	Risk Assessment
Adverse Event Analysis	1	6	14
Continuous Monitoring	6	16	9

Co-occurrence between Detect vs Protect

	Awareness and Training	Data Security	Identity Management, Authentication, and Access Control	Platform Security	Technology Infrastructure Resilience
Adverse Event Analysis	45	6	3	4	7
Continuous Monitoring	18	49	2	43	44

Co-occurrence between Detect vs Respond

	Incident Analysis	Incident Management	Incident Mitigation	Incident Response Reporting and Communication
Adverse Event Analysis	13	12	10	5
Continuous Monitoring	50	35	32	12

Co-occurrence between Detect vs Govern

	Cybersecurity Supply Chain Risk Management	Organizational Context	Oversight	Policy	Risk Management Strategy	Roles, Responsibilities, and Authorities
Adverse Event Analysis	9	0	1	0	12	1
Continuous Monitoring	6	4	13	5	16	6

Co-occurrence between Detect vs Recover

	Incident Recovery Communication	Incident Recovery Plan Execution
Adverse Event Analysis	0	1
Continuous Monitoring	0	5

Appendix G: CO-OCCURRENCE ANALYSIS TABLES

Co-occurrence between Govern vs Identify

	Asset Management	Improvement	Risk Assessment
Cybersecurity Supply Chain Risk Management	9	18	28
Organizational Context	19	60	63
Oversight	12	41	52
Policy	5	16	22
Risk Management Strategy	6	42	37
Roles, Responsibilities, and Authorities	3	16	13

Co-occurrence between Govern vs Protect

	Awareness and Training	Data Security	Identity Management, Authentication, and Access Control	Platform Security	Technology Infrastructure Resilience
Cybersecurity Supply Chain Risk Management	9	10	3	7	6
Organizational Context	2	6	1	7	6
Oversight	7	6	0	8	6
Policy	1	9	2	8	8
Risk Management Strategy	10	14	0	9	15
Roles, Responsibilities, and Authorities	3	0	2	3	4

Co-occurrence between Govern vs Recover

	Incident Recovery Communication	Incident Recovery Plan Execution
Cybersecurity Supply Chain Risk Management	2	2
Organizational Context	1	1
Oversight	2	4
Policy	3	4
Risk Management Strategy	3	9
Roles, Responsibilities, and Authorities	0	3

Appendix G: CO-OCCURRENCE ANALYSIS TABLES

Co-occurrence between Govern vs Respond

	Incident Analysis	Incident Management	Incident Mitigation	Incident Response Reporting and Communication
Cybersecurity Supply Chain Risk Management	4	2	3	2
Organizational Context	7	5	7	2
Oversight	11	9	8	1
Policy	2	5	9	2
Risk Management Strategy	10	10	18	3
Roles, Responsibilities, and Authorities	6	5	3	4

Co-occurrence between Identify vs Protect

	Awareness and Training	Data Security	Identity Management, Authentication, and Access Control	Platform Security	Technology Infrastructure Resilience
Asset Management	3	5	2	2	5
Improvement	7	11	3	11	23
Risk Assessment	7	9	2	15	21

Co-occurrence between Identify vs Recover

	Incident Recovery Communication	Incident Recovery Plan Execution
Asset Management	2	2
Improvement	3	5
Risk Assessment	4	5

Co-occurrence between Identify vs Respond

	Incident Analysis	Incident Management	Incident Mitigation	Incident Response Reporting and Communication
Asset Management	0	1	0	3
Improvement	13	9	15	1
Risk Assessment	17	18	12	2

Appendix G: CO-OCCURRENCE ANALYSIS TABLES

Co-occurrence between Protect vs Recover

	Incident Recovery Communication	Incident Recovery Plan Execution
Awareness and Training	0	2
Data Security	1	2
Identity Management, Authentication, and Access Control	0	2
Platform Security	1	6
Technology Infrastructure Resilience	0	4

Co-occurrence between Protect vs Respond

	Incident Analysis	Incident Management	Incident Mitigation	Incident Response Reporting and Communication
Awareness and Training	8	6	7	4
Data Security	37	26	34	4
Identity Management, Authentication, and Access Control	2	1	1	1
Platform Security	25	27	41	4
Technology Infrastructure Resilience	30	30	30	3

Co-occurrence between Recover vs Respond

	Incident Analysis	Incident Management	Incident Mitigation	Incident Response Reporting and Communication
Incident Recovery Communication	0	0	0	1
Incident Recovery Plan Execution	3	7	11	1